

RURITAGE

Heritage for Rural Regeneration

Exploitation Strategy

D6.1

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1. Technical sheet

Project Full title		Rural regeneration through systemic heritage-led strategies	
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2. List of Abbreviations and Acronyms Used

CA	Consortium Agreement
CNH	Cultural and Natural Heritage
CoR	European Committee of the Regions
D	Deliverable
DSS	Decision Support System
EC	European Commission
EIB	European Investment Bank
EM	Exploitation Manager
EP	European Parliament
ICOMOS	International Council on Monuments and Sites
JPICH	Joint Programming Initiative on Cultural Heritage
M	Month
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
R	Replicator
RHH	Rural Heritage Hub
RIS3	Research and Innovation Strategies for Smart Specialisation
RM	Role Model
SIA	Systemic Innovation Area
UN	United Nations
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
WP	Work Package

3. Project Summary

European rural areas embody outstanding examples of Cultural and Natural Heritage (CNH) that should be safeguarded and promoted as a driver for competitiveness, sustainability and inclusive growth and development. To this end, RURITAGE establishes a new heritage-led rural regeneration paradigm aimed at turning rural areas into sustainable development demonstration laboratories, through the enhancement of their unique CNH potential. To this end, RURITAGE has identified 6 Systematic Innovation Areas (SIAs):

- Pilgrimage;
- Sustainable Local Food Production;
- Migration;
- Arts and Festivals;
- Resilience;
- Landscape Management.

These SIAs are integrated within cross-cutting themes to showcase heritage potential as a powerful engine for economic, social and environmental development of rural areas.

The knowledge derived from 14 Role Models (RMs), analysed and evaluated within the project, along with additional Role Models recruited through an Open Call, will initially be transferred to 6 selected Replicators across Europe. Through a multi-level and multi-directional process of knowledge transfer, RMs will mentor and support the Replicators in the development and implementation of their strategies and, at the same time, will further increase their own knowledge and capacities. A robust monitoring system will assist this process.

Local Rural Heritage Hubs (RHHs), which will gather and engage with stakeholders and civil society, will be established in Role Models and Replicators. In Replicators these will work as Living Labs where heritage-led rural regeneration strategies will be co-created and implemented, whilst in Role Models these will reinforce the ownership of CNH and further drive their development potential.

Role Models and Replicators will also benefit from the RURITAGE Resources Ecosystem – a set of exploitable tools including, amongst others, a rural landscape mapping tool (RURITAGE Atlas) and a Replication Toolbox within an online and interoperable platform. These tools will foster knowledge building, providing evidence and supporting replication and up-scaling activities for the implementation of heritage-led regeneration strategies and plans, contributing to mainstream heritage in Regional, National, European and Global Policies.

To ensure further reach, exploitability and impact from the outset:

- A call for additional Replicators was successfully launched (D 6.2 – M12), that achieved >100 enquires form worldwide, with the following outcomes:
 - 87 eligible applications received from 37 countries, with invitations to join the project issued to relevant organisations with the following final uptake:
 - 10 additional Replicators selected to participate with expenses paid by the project
 - 8 more Rs selected to participate in relevant activities at their own expense
 - 38 digital Rs provided with access to online tools
- A RURITAGE branding strategy is in the process of being developed and implemented, which will include a marketing strategy and communication plan (D6.3 – M18)
- Storytelling videos for each of the 6 Replicators as part of their branding strategy (D 6.4 – M18)
- New skills for innovative management of CNH in rural areas will be delivered through a Masters Programme, scheduled to begin in Sept 2020, and Summer Schools beginning in Summer 2020 (D 6.5).

Later in the project, Policy Recommendations for the integration of CNH within RIS3 strategies and an International Level White Paper on CNH as a driver for sustainable development will also be produced as important exploitation deliverables.

4. Exploitation Planning

RURITAGE establishes a new heritage-led rural regeneration paradigm aimed at turning rural areas into sustainable development demonstration laboratories, through the enhancement of their unique Cultural and Natural Heritage (CNH) potential.

WP6 is devoted to defining an effective exploitation strategy to properly address the market uptake of RURITAGE's products and tools developed during the project, thus contributing to position the EU as a world leader in heritage-led strategies. Task 6.1 is dedicated to the design of the exploitation strategy to plan for the commercial deployment and sustainability of the project results. The Strategy is a living document that will be subject to annual revisions including the completion of Action Plans for each Exploitable Result during the lifetime of the Project.

This Exploitation Strategy for RURITAGE is designed to focus on the development of user-optimised results from the project, to multiply the impact and uptake of the proposed solutions in order to fully achieve their exploitation potential. To this end the Exploitation Strategy provides a summary of the project, gives an overview of the main exploitation results that will be delivered and the latest proposals of how the consortium partners intend to use and promote these results to foster their uptake both during and after the lifetime of the project.

The main Exploitable Results of the project are identified as follows:

1. RURITAGE Systematic Innovation Areas (SIAs)
2. RURITAGE Branding and Storytelling Videos
3. RURITAGE Atlas
4. RURITAGE DSS
5. My Cult-Rural Toolkit
6. Serious Game Kit
7. Summer Schools
8. Professional Masters Programme

The Exploitation potential of these results will also build on the outputs of other relevant deliverables, including:

- Call for Additional Replicators and selected Replicators Agreement (Del 6.2 – May 2019 (M12))
- Policy Recommendations for the Integration of CNH in RIS3 (Del 6.6 – M42)
- White Paper – CNH as a driver for sustainable development in the EU and beyond (Del 6.7 – M42)

4.1 Exploitation Objectives

The RURITAGE Exploitation Strategy aims to guarantee and magnify the impact of the projects results, by defining the activities to be undertaken (what, how and by whom) in order to ensure their effective exploitation both during and beyond the lifetime of the project, with the main objectives listed as follows:

- Ensure that exploitable results are identified, optimised, user-friendly, transferable and adaptable as necessary
- Develop appropriate action plans, business models and financial mechanisms to support the deployment and sustainability of the project results to achieve their expected targets
- Identify and reach the target audience through use of appropriate communication/delivery channels and exploitation routes
- Foster the RURITAGE paradigm and contribute to positioning the EU as World Leader in heritage-led rural regeneration strategies

The Exploitation Strategy reflects sound analysis of market needs, trends, potential users, and sustainability. The target stakeholders and users will be precisely identified and exploitation routes defined in order to reach those target markets and encourage widespread promotion, uptake and use of the projects results.

5. Exploitation Management

The Exploitation Manager (EM) has overall responsibility for the exploitation of the project results. The Exploitation Manager is **James Donlon from WestBIC**, officially appointed during the Project kick-off meeting. The exploitation activities will be coordinated by the Exploitation Manager in collaboration with Task Leaders and the Steering Committee.

The Exploitation Manager shall:

- a) Prepare the master plan for the exploitation strategy
- b) Coordinate the implementation of exploitation activities
- c) Contribute to proper exploitation of the results by assisting Partners to prepare adequate Action Plans and Business Plans to maximise the impact of exploitable results
- d) Monitor the delivery and impact of exploitation measures.

The Exploitation Manager (EM) participates on the Management Board and on the Project Steering Committee, who will oversee the required exploitation activities.

Led by the Exploitation Manager, the Exploitation Strategy is developed with the support of Task Leaders and Consortium Partners. It also includes co-ordination and integration with other relevant Work Packages, given the cross-cutting nature of the Strategy.

Two exploitation workshops are planned, whose goals are:

- to discuss the most promising results and formulate first hypotheses related to the related potential business models (at project mid-term)
- to obtain agreement on the final exploitation actions to be undertaken (toward the end of the project)

These will provide input for the finalisation of the exploitation strategy and Action Plans for the commercial deployment of project results, which will be released by month 48.

The final workshop will also particularly give input to the Business Plans for each of the key exploitable results. Steering Committee members and relevant partners for exploitation activities will participate within those workshops. Relevant session dedicated to the exploitation strategy will also be held during GA meetings, thus including all the interested partners (i.e RMs and Rs) in decisions concerning exploitation of the results.

5.1 Role of Partners/Beneficiaries in Exploitation

Task leaders will be assisted in developing Action Plans that can be implemented for each Exploitable Result listed in Section 13 of this document. To ensure a consistent and comprehensive approach, these Action Plans will follow the template headings agreed in Section 12 of this strategy. These Action Plans will be included as an Appendix to the Exploitation Strategy as they are developed during the lifetime of the project.

Subject to any restrictions due to the protection of intellectual property, security rules or legitimate interests, all participants that receive project funding shall, through appropriate means, use its best efforts to disseminate and exploit the results it owns or jointly owns/develops, or have them exploited by another entity.

A suitable organisation structure, comprising relevant project partners, will be put in place to facilitate the efficient management and further development and exploitation of relevant project tools and results of a collaborative nature beyond the lifetime of the project itself. As a multiplier, this new structure can also foster further collaboration by exploring and developing related opportunities in this sector in the future.

6. Intellectual Property Rights

In line with the Grant Agreement, the Consortium has a policy of protecting the project's results, whenever results are expected to be commercially exploitable and whenever this protection is possible, reasonable and justified. Where this is applicable, the necessary steps to protect the associated IP will be included in the Action Plan for the relevant project results. Already the following IPR issues and opportunities are identified:

- Trademarking of the Brand (D 6.3)
- Copyright of the Storytelling Videos for the 6 Rs (D 6.4)

IPR will be managed through the detailed internal IP Protection Plan that will be developed in WP8.

7. Ownership of Results

The ownership of results is strictly controlled by the Consortium Agreement (CA) - Section 8, which includes all provisions related to the Ownership of Results, Joint Ownership of Results, Use of Results and Transfer of Results. Specifically relating to jointly owned results which could be commercially exploited, including but not limited to RURITAGE Systematic Innovation Areas (SIAs), RURITAGE branding, RURITAGE Decision Support System (DSS), Serious Game Kit, RURITAGE Atlas, My Cult-Rural Toolkit; these will be the subject of discussion among the parties that participate in the development of such results. The parties shall make their best efforts to negotiate in good faith and finalise joint ownership agreements before the end of the project.

8. Access Rights for Exploitation

Access Rights are described and agreed in Section 9 of the Consortium Agreement. Specifically Section 9.4 covers Access Rights for Exploitation, which in general shall be granted on Fair and Reasonable conditions, whilst Access Rights to Results for internal non-commercial research activities and for non-commercial education purposes shall be granted on a royalty-free basis. Any addition after the signature of the CA requires a decision of the Coordination Board and the Steering Committee.

9. Data Management

Data Management in the context of the Exploitation Strategy mainly concerns data gathered in the development of the Exploitable Results themselves. This is governed by the Data Management Plan to be developed and implemented for the overall Project. Any additional data that may be gathered as part of the delivery of individual Exploitation Plans will be subject to this Data Management Plan.

10. Target Audiences for Exploitation

The target audiences of RURITAGE exploitation activities are closely correlated with those of Work Package 7 (WP7 - Communication and Dissemination). Firstly, the main project target groups are identified, as follows:

- Policymakers and Public Institutions
- Researchers and Knowledge Providers
- Civil Society
- Businesses and Investors

Within these target groups, specific audiences/sub-groups are identified and further defined as primary or secondary target audiences for RURITAGE dissemination and exploitation activities. These are listed in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Primary and Secondary Target Audiences for RURITAGE results dissemination and exploitation

Policymakers and public institutions	Researchers and knowledge providers	Businesses and investors	Civil society
Primary			
Local administrations of RMs and Rs, particularly departments responsible for CNH management and sustainable local development Regional agencies and national authorities responsible for rural development, CNH management, social inclusion, tourism, employment European institutions and instruments: EC, EP, CoR, JPICH, EIB International organisations: UNESCO, UNDP, UN World Tourism Organisation, ICOMOS Funding institutions	Researchers focusing on rural development and the role of heritage in sustainable development Researchers focusing on participatory governance, community empowerment, CNH management	Investors, incl. LAGs, foundations, banks Creative industries in RMs and Rs SMEs in RMs and Rs Service providers involved in CNH management in RMs and Rs The tourism industry in RMs and Rs The construction industry in RMs and Rs	Residents of RMs and Rs Local community associations Local NGOs focused on CNH management, local development, employment Local media NGOs and networks focused on rural development, CNH management, social inclusion (national, European, international)
Secondary			
National agencies responsible for SIA topics Relevant media	Researchers focusing on SIAs topics Relevant media	Business associations of the tourism industry Business associations of the construction industry Business associations of cultural and creative industries Service providers involved in CNH management (beyond RMs and Rs) Relevant media	NGOs and networks focused on SIAs topics

10.1 Communication Channels

In co-operation with the Dissemination Plan, specific communication strategies will be defined according to the target market (audience) identified by the Business Models for each of the Exploitable Results. This is aimed at deriving the maximum exposure, to achieve and hopefully exceed agreed targets, in terms of market uptake.

Already, channels that will be used for project publicity and results are listed in the Dissemination Plan, and include:

Project Website and Social Media Channels	Media Dissemination
Partners Communication Channels and Networks	SIA Webinars
Project Newsletter (Annual)	Scientific Dissemination
Press Releases	Final Conference

Additionally, other activities that will be used to foster exploitation include:

- Calls for Additional Role Models and Replicators for inclusion in project activities, including knowledge transfer workshops
- Summer Schools and Master Programme to be developed and delivered to share learning and build new skills
- Policy Recommendations for the Integration of CNH within RIS3, including presentation Workshop in Brussels
- White paper 'CNH as a Driver for Sustainable Development in the EU and Beyond' for promotion and dissemination at international level, including developing countries

Specific exploitation routes will be identified and agreed when the Action Plans and Business Models are developed for each Exploitable Result.

11. Exploitation Action Planning

To maximise their potential impact, each Exploitable Result will be subject to the development of an Exploitation Action Plan according to the following key headings, to ensure a consistent and comprehensive approach to their elaboration:

- Title and Characterisation of Exploitable Result
- IPR measures taken or intended
- Owners and Key Beneficiaries involved
- Stakeholders/ Target Users
- Proposed Exploitation Route(s)
- Benefits (Impact Indicators) and Targets
- Business Model and Sustainability Plan
- Timeframe and Roadmap for Exploitation
- Barriers/Risk to be Overcome
- List of Proposed Actions, Responsibility and Timescale for completion

For efficiency these Action Plans will be developed in advance and updated according to the technological and/or market readiness of the Exploitable Results themselves. In some cases, where necessary, the timing will also be scheduled to facilitate delivery of other parts of the project.

12. List and Description of Exploitable Results

<h3>12.1 RURITAGE Systemic Innovation Areas (SIAs)</h3>	Task Leader: UNIBO
<p>RURITAGE establishes a novel heritage-led rural regeneration paradigm through the identification of 6 SIAs (Pilgrimage, Sustainable Local Food Production, Migration, Art and Festivals, Resilience, Integrated Landscape management) and involving an integrated, multi-stakeholder and transdisciplinary development approach.</p> <p>Together with the provision of tools and methods for replication (e.g. Replication ToolBox, RURITAGE Resources Ecosystem), this enhances its potential to become a standardised procedure to be exploited and adopted for heritage-led regeneration in rural areas. An Exploitation Action Plan will be developed to provide access to the generated knowledge along with the potential for delivery of advisory services by project partners or via a spin-off entity. This will be complemented by the other RURITAGE tools along with the RURITAGE Branding and Atlas to provide a comprehensive methodological approach to benefit rural regions.</p>	Other beneficiaries involved: ALL
<h3>12.2 RURITAGE Branding including Story-telling Videos</h3>	Task Leader: BITN
<p>The RURITAGE branding will be conceived as a European brand for rural regeneration based on the six SIAs of the RURITAGE paradigm uniting local distinctiveness, SIA specificities and territorial excellence in one aggregated brand of rural regeneration. The brand will be available to Role Models and Replicator regions that adopt the RURITAGE development approach to foster the heritage-led regeneration of rural territories across the EU and beyond. .</p> <p>The marketing strategy for the Brand will allow relevant businesses and other entities from these regions to join and use the brand, in line with standard criteria/guidelines that will be set for its use. In this way it will be developed as a replicable instrument that can be upscaled and applied to other rural areas interested in taking part in the RURITAGE network.</p> <p>The Branding will be complemented by Storytelling Videos, capturing local emotions, identity, values, experiences and traditions, that will be developed for all Replicators in the project to reshape their image. These videos will highlight tangible results and describe how effective regeneration strategies have been inspired from and applied to rural areas. They will form part of the local marketing strategy for Replicators and will contribute to the overall launch of the RURITAGE brand in Europe.</p> <p>As a key part of the project that links with other elements, the overall strategy for the exploitation of the Brand, including its business model, selection criteria, etc. will be developed during the first 18 months of the project.</p>	Other beneficiaries involved: UNIBO UNESCO ICLEI WestBIC
<h3>12.3 RURITAGE Atlas</h3>	Task Leader: POLITO
<p>RURITAGE will map the multiple functions of rural areas and ‘human-landscape’ interactions in a novel way, making available data, maps, images, models, historical and topographical representations and other relevant information, along with the RURITAGE Practices Repository and Inventory of Lessons Learned, included in a comprehensive RURITAGE Atlas. RURITAGE Atlas allows a visualisation of the CNH area through a place-based map. The geo-referred elements will link to a database</p>	Other beneficiaries involved: ALL

<p>where cultural, heritage, historical, tourist and more information will be available. By doing so, the Atlas mapping will provide an easy access to relevant information for different user groups.</p> <p>This innovative tool will enable a number of exploitation possibilities, both for further research activities and for providing a service to rural communities committed to undergoing a process of heritage-led rural regeneration.</p> <p>The RURITAGE Atlas, as an interactive map, will provide strategic information useful for the cultural tourism sector and the promotion of cultural heritage in rural areas by linking intangible heritage to places and by contextualising geographical and historical information. The same interface will allow decision makers to access economic and strategic information, by zooming into a specific place on the map.</p> <p>RURITAGE Atlas can also be replicated and further exploited in different frameworks and at different mapping scales. For example, it can be transferred from Rural to Urban areas, and from a larger scale (RMs and Rs) to a smaller scale (city, districts, etc.).</p>	
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<p>12.4 RURITAGE Decision Support System (DSS)</p>	<p>Task Leader: ALM</p>
<p>The Ruritage DSS will provide a guide to replicators to develop their regeneration strategies based on analysis of the good practices and Inventory of Lessons Learnt from the Role Models. To do this, the DSS analyses the range of “best practice” activities that Role Models have undertaken in the past (Inventory of Lessons Learned) and from this, generates potential time lines of next steps that may be taken by Replicators to achieve their own development objectives. The choice of relevant experiences for the Replicators is, initially, based on a similarity search of the replicators context or on the KPI's that a replicators wishes to influence (e.g. support local production, or attract more tourists). It is assumed that a range of approaches will be used to best serve the search for "best practices" of the replicators. For each approach a software agent will be created that negotiates with the agents of other outcomes in order to provide the best overall advice.</p> <p>The DSS will be presented as an online interactive dashboard that allows users to create and change Replicator profiles, with will provide a visual map of solution combinations together with illustrative diagrams giving insight into the matching scores for different dimensions The system platform will be accessible through the RURITAGE website. During the course of the RURITAGE project, ALM will continuously extend the DSS with new functionalities and possibilities, including integration of the DSS with the RHH and RURITAGE ATLAS.</p> <p>After the end of the project, exploitation of the DSS by a new spin-off company or joint venture is foreseen.</p>	<p>Other beneficiaries involved:</p> <p>TECNALIA CRS UNIBO</p>

<p>12.5 My Cult-Rural Toolkit</p>	<p>Task Leader: UoP</p>
<p>Existing technologies (Rate-my-View and Landscape-Connect Apps) will be integrated with PGIS and Tagscape methodologies to develop a powerful co-monitoring tool, that can be exploited for collecting images and feedback from citizens, including CNH in diversified contexts.</p>	<p>Other beneficiaries involved:</p> <p>tbc</p>

<p>The proposed exploitation approach will include the development of a dedicated app, along with a facilitated workshop service targeted at municipalities and others wishing to adopt this approach.</p> <p>As part of the exploitation, UOP expects to continue with the further development and promotion of these technologies, with potential for targeting other fields and uses, e.g. safety/security, transport infrastructures damage/breakdown, customer service evaluation in retail etc. This may be done directly through UoP, or depending on feasibility a spin-off or a start-up will be considered, to further develop and manage the dedicated App.</p>	
<h3>12.6 Serious Game Kit</h3>	<p>Task Leader: CRS</p>
<p>Simulation games and workshop scenarios are combined in a Serious Game Kit to be integrated within the RURITAGE Replicator Tool Box. This can be downloaded, printed, prepared and played by institutions interested in training and in using the game's DIY approach to develop their CNH projects.</p> <p>This Serious Game Kit can be downloaded as a complimentary service or it may be personalised and tailored to specific needs of companies or municipalities willing to adopt and make use of the service.</p>	<p>Other beneficiaries involved:</p>
<h3>12.7 Summer Schools</h3>	<p>Task Leader: UNIBO</p>
<p>Two Summer schools will be organised during the project timeframe, targeting Masters and PhD students, along with civil servants and employees in Local Authorities, local organisations, NGO's etc. The first one is planned for Summer 2020.</p> <p>These Summer schools will create additional project dissemination and exploitation opportunities for the RURITAGE paradigm, to foster the uptake of its tools and exploitable results, whilst the content for the Summer Schools will have further replicability beyond the lifetime of the project.</p>	<p>Other beneficiaries involved:</p> <p>POLITO SAVONIA UAS All University Partners</p>
<h3>12.8 Professional Masters' Programme</h3>	<p>Task Leader: UNIBO</p>
<p>Based on the best-practice learning from the RURITAGE project and current experiences internationally, e.g. <i>Masters in World Heritage and Cultural Projects for Development</i> (UNESCO), a Professional Masters Programme will be set up and promoted to provide practitioners, civil servants and employees of NGOs etc with the necessary skills for innovative management of CNH in rural areas.</p> <p>Two editions of the Masters course are envisaged during the project duration, which will be a useful product for communicating the RURITAGE Paradigm, and the project outputs and results. The first edition is planned for Sept 2020 as a joint title between UNIBO and POLITO. The 2nd edition will build on this pilot and is expected to include additional University partners in the project. The Programme will also be available for further exploitation after the project timeframe.</p>	<p>Other beneficiaries involved:</p> <p>All university partners; UNESCO</p>

13. Timescale for Delivery of Exploitation Action Plans and Deliverables

Exploitation Action Plans will be prepared for each Exploitable Result as they are developed, and will be included as an Appendix to this Exploitation Strategy.

This will be updated as each result is developed and the Action Plan is completed. These will be living documents and will evolve as the project progresses and as new opportunities are realised for the Results achieved.

The list of Exploitable Results and the target completion date are included in the following table:

Table 2: List of Exploitable Results and Envisaged Timescale for Delivery

	Title of the Exploitable Result(s)	Target Date(s)
1	RURITAGE Systematic Innovation Areas (SIAs)	M36
2	RURITAGE Branding including Storytelling Videos	M8-18
3	RURITAGE Atlas	M12
4	RURITAGE Decision Support System (DSS)	M24
5	My Cult-Rural Toolkit	M18
6	Serious Game Kit	M24
7	Summer Schools	M26, M38
8	Professional Master Programme	M42-48

The envisaged timescales for other deliverables in the Exploitation Work Package are as follows:

Table 3: List of Other Deliverables and Timescale for Delivery

Deliverable	Title of the Exploitable Result(s)	Target Date(s)
6.2	Call for Additional Replicators and Selected Replicator Agreement	(Complete M12)
6.6	Policy Recommendations for the Integration of CNH within RIS3	M42
6.7	White Paper 'CNH as a driver for sustainable development in EU and beyond'	M42

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